

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN SUPPORT OF ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS IN ESP CLASSES

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Annotation. This work is aimed to focus on the advantages of incorporating digital technologies in the English language classes, mostly in the support of the speaking development skills, one of the productive skills which students are always into trouble in improving. This paper involves in the challenges and possible ways of how to handle the difficulties by digitalizing that learner of ESP may come across in speaking. Besides it covers the importance of using digital technologies for teaching purposes and the practice of different Apps concerning learners' interest, this article informs about strategies, methods of effective and appropriate use of various digital tools and the ways of how to put all these techniques into practice.

Key words: digitalization, speaking, ESP, context, methodology, development, technologies, implementation, input, output, tools, engineering, classroom, techniques, difficulties, solutions, students' needs, APPs, platforms, factors, experience, computers, Flipgrid, Zo talk, Fluent.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur ilmiy maqola talabalar uchun doimo mushkul bo'lib kelgan, ularning o'rganishi va rivojlatirishida qiyinchiliklarga duch kelgan ko'nikmalaridan biri bo'lgan: gapirish maxoratini qanday qilib tez, samarali va oson yo'l bilan, nofilolog o'rganuvchilarning qiziqishlarini va bilim mahoratlarini, muxtojliklarini etiborga olgan holda, turli xil platforma va raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida rivojlantirishga, yaxshilashga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada gapirish ko'nikmalarini yaxshilash uchun yuzaga keladigan muammolar va ularning ma'qul yechimlari, turli raqamlashtirish texnologiyalari, va samarali, qiziqarli o'qitish metodikalari, raqamli vositalarining gapirish mahoratini oshirishda ishlatiladigan aniq platforma va saytlarning nomlari ham keltirib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamlashtirish, gapirish, ESP, kontekst, metodologiya, texnologiyalar, amalga oshirish, kiritish, chiqish, muhandislik, sinf, texnikalar, qiyinchiliklar, yechimlar, talabalar ehtiyojlari, APPlar, platformalar, omillar, tajriba, kompyuterlar, Flipgrid, Zo talk, Fluent.

Аннотация. Эта работа направлена на то, чтобы сосредоточиться на преимуществах внедрения цифровых технологий на уроках английского языка, в основном на поддержке навыков развития разговорной речи, одного из продуктивных навыков, с улучшением которого у студентов всегда возникают проблемы. В этой статье рассматриваются проблемы и возможные способы решения трудностей путем оцифровки, с которыми может столкнуться изучающий ESP в разговорной речи. Помимо того, что в этой статье рассматривается важность использования цифровых технологий в учебных целях и практика использования различных приложений, представляющих интерес для учащихся, в этой статье рассказывается о стратегиях, методах эффективного и надлежащего использования различных цифровых инструментов, а также о способах применения всех этих методов на практике.

Ключевые слова: *цифровизация, говорение, ESP, контекст, методология, разработка, технологии, реализация, ввод, вывод, инструменты, проектирование, класс, методы, трудности, решения, потребности студентов, приложения, платформы, факторы, опыт, компьютеры, Flipgrid, Zo talk, Fluent.*

Relying on digitalization in information technology integration, which is very questionable in 21st century is rapidly developing day by day. Besides, economy and manufacturing, utilizing digital tools in the education system is playing a significant role. However, there are enough problems to implement digital technologies in the classroom. For instance, lack of computers, some other technical tools, internet connection, enough knowledge and experience to teach. But it is becoming possible to deal with those all problems nowadays. As we are living in the modern era, it is required to apply for new methods and new ways of teaching English to our learners. According to Amy M. Johnson, Matthew E. Jacovina, Devin G. Russell, and Christian M. Soto (2016) “Technology is the most powerful factor shaping the educational landscape today. In many education institutions, computers, tablets and other technical tools are being provided in order to increase the level of technology in the classrooms, enhance the quality of education, furthermore, different programs are being organized to improve teachers’ and students’ knowledge about information technology”.

Technology integration into classroom is an alternative way of teaching in order to improve learners’ knowledge in schools, colleges, and higher educations. For instance, in English classes, traditional teaching, which is grammar translation method is out of date in this new era, because students cannot productively enhance their all-language skills by translating from one into another language. They are guided into one direction only, which is grammar or speaking and writing only relying on the book, and as for the other skills, they have lack of knowledge, cause of the shortage of technology or guidelines by teacher. Or else they may be learning other listening, speaking, and writing skills with the help of just papers, books, or oral activities, it is also good when skills are taught in integration, but once we have a technology why cannot we use that in the classroom. It is very effective to our students’ motivation as well. Because they are interested in different types of digits like computer, mobile phone, etc. Students want to get along with everyday news via different mass media. As they are always busy with their mobile phones, so they want to use them in the class too. Anyway, if we do not let them use during the lesson, they may lose their interest and do not want to listen to the teacher. We can involve our learners’ integrating digital tools in the classroom and conduct a productive lesson. It really depends on the teacher’s knowledge about using technology to have an interesting and interactive lesson. Suzana Cabek Tingley states that most people prefer to spend their time playing with their mobile phones rather than reading books. As it is so important to apply for digitalization in the class, any teacher should feel how much they need to integrate different technology in their lesson plan.

According to some research, in many institutions, digital technology can effect on the educational system, especially students’ behavior badly. Cause they might be busy with their mobile phone during the class. It is very difficult for teachers to control their students as they have an opportunity to have a device to play different online games. They cannot help playing and as a result, they do not want to listen and pay attention to the lesson. Even these all games in their phone that they are playing may go round in their mind and that might interrupt students to get proper information to improve their knowledge.

On the other hand, digitalizing the classroom is the most effective way of delivering the content and involving the student's attention to the lesson, as they are keen on knowing and being engaged in the technology rather than just traditionally focused on the paper based methodology. As an example, speaking, as it is mentioned is one of the most challenging skills among, to produce fluently, hence if students are technologically attracted by the use of different apps, they can easily acquire the most difficult aspects of spoken English. Because they always follow up- to- date technologies in their daily bases.

As Christophel Sol Cruz states, applying for digital technology in the class does not mean only learning the target language but also utilizing the language itself in every sphere by social media. In order to get in contact, to share some information, and to solve some problems, students have to use different applications and those all applications are in various languages. It is very necessary for teachers to know how to use digital technology in the class, because digitalization can open the door to the world.

These years, it is very difficult to get good results from students with the help of just papers and notebook, which is traditional way of teaching, as they want to be busy with their gadget even in the classroom. It is impossible for youngsters to imagine their life without their mobile phones, because they want to be aware of updated news going on in the world. Social media like: Instagram, Telegram, Facebook involve young learners a lot. Cause of these, teachers have to think something new to use their gadget in the class to have interesting and productive lessons. Integrating technology into classroom can improve the quality of the education, as it is a new and powerful way to involve students' attention. As this papers is mostly about speaking involvement, there are different Apps to help both teachers and students to evolve the production of speaking. Speaking and writing both are considered as productive skills as leaners have to produce them rather than receive like reading and listening. The students of ESP need more speaking to communicate for their own purposes, so the most important skill they have to acquire first is speaking. For this reason, learners should be engaged in the most effective and easy ways to learn the aspects and features of speaking. Once students utter a word they should know where to stress and how to intonate like native speaker, the best solution and way to make it possible is utilizing different tools. For instance: Flipgrid is highly evaluated app which can help teachers and learners to develop speaking together with listening. Because, there are different functions like timing, messaging, video taking, posting different questions for students to respond, updating the responses, reposting, texting, etc. Once the teachers post the questions or prompts, they can send the link to the target learners to submit their responses, they can set the time, or change the topic a bit later, they can be automatically updated once it is finished. So, this app is rather productive and easy to apply for teachers as well.

Before, instructors relied on paper-based tests, which is out of date nowadays. They wasted their time, money, as they had to print all tests out and distribute to the students. Comparing now, teachers can create online test and easily apply for their students in the classroom and for sure, it is much easier and more interesting. However, there should be availabilities for digitalized lesson, like computers, internet connection, projectors and other devices to conduct the lesson productively integrating technology in the classroom. Unfortunately, not all rooms are equipped with those mentioned technologies, so teachers even though they are educated in term of technology, even they are able to apply for different applications besides Flipgrid mentioned, to improve learners' speaking skills and knowledge, they are limited cause of the shortage of the digital tools in the class. As Brendon Hyndman (2018) states, if we do not solve those all problems related to technology, we might create further

issues for the target learners in the future. Furthermore, according to the data collection of Warschauer and Zheng: it is important to have all rooms equipped with technologies fully, but unfortunately, both teachers and students are struggling with the absence of devices in many countries, they have to rely on papers, pens and board having just traditional way of learning and teaching.

The main rationale of why learners do not have a chance to be educated in integration of technology is the teachers' knowledge in digitalization. Most teachers are not able to teach involving digital tools in the classroom as they have lack of knowledge to utilize. Firstly, they should be familiar and then they can teach students using different digits. Instructors might prefer to teach just in a usual way as they do not know how to integrate digital technology and they might think that utilizing technology in the class may negatively influence on students' behavior, character and knowledge. Cause of this reason they conduct their lesson based on old strategies, which are boring for learners and as a result, students can lose their temper.

Utilizing technology in the classroom has different benefits and advantages. It is the best way to let students be dominated in the class, as they know digital tools even better than the teacher does. There used to be a teacher who was in the center of the class, taking more, participating more, and acting more. However, in this modern life, students can show themselves off as a leader leading and motivating each other more. Students can also take various responsibilities like controlling each other, helping with the device that they are using to connect to the internet or to teach the instructions of how to use them, which are very interesting and involving process for them.

Nowadays, English language is being taught as a second language in many countries, all functions and instructions in different digits are in English so it would be much easier for both teachers and students if they manage to have a digitalized lesson so they can easily understand everything there to control. There are so many application and platforms, which an English teacher can use in the class to evolve not only speaking, but also all four skills and some other skills related to English. Each can surely influence on further development of students' knowledge. It is much more comfortable to understand and learn through those platforms, namely Padlet, Flipgrid, Kahoot, My google doc, My quiz, Jeopardy, and so on. Each has its own purposes and methods to implement.

Implementing these apps into classroom has had influenced in teaching and learning process, so that's why most teachers and students are keen on integrating digital technology to get productive input and output. For example, I use kahoot.it to involve my students in clarifying the result of the input, or just to test them to identify their current level. This kind of online test make students be engaged and interested in the content of the topic. Kahoot.it is the best tool to involve learners into classroom, as it has different and several functions and multiple options: test forms to make. There teachers utilize multiple choice, true and false, sentence completion, open ending questions types of tests which are very practical to create.

The other overmentioned applications listed above are also so reliable to use for different purposes and skills in the classroom to get the students motivation. As the speaking is one of the most problematic skill to improve among students and even sometimes teachers, I with my one of my students created a web site which can help to showcase speaking and listening enhancement, which is named Zo -Talk. There teachers can run into different functions which can help to engage the students in several TED talks, podcasts, TEDx and different topics to discuss and even teachers can create video tasks for students to respond.

In conclusion, technology can give different opportunities for both teachers and students in term of speaking: to teach and get information easier, to visualize, to be engaged and motivated, to be centered, to be able to share fast, and to have a very interesting and productive lesson.

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